

ASSESSING THE PERFORMANCE OF PUPILS AND TEACHERS IN MULTIGRADE CLASSES IN THE CITY OF ILAGAN

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ABSTRACT

This study looked into the performance of pupils and teachers in multigrade classes in the City of Ilagan. Utilizing a descriptive research design, the study analyzed the profiles of 34 multigrade teachers and 476 pupils from Grades V and VI across three districts. Data were gathered using structured questionnaires, interviews, and official records such as teachers' CBPAST ratings and pupils' academic performance reports. Statistical tools, including frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and chi-square tests, were employed to examine relationships and differences in performance. Findings revealed that multigrade teachers, predominantly young and professionally trained, demonstrated proficient performance. Pupils exhibited average academic performance, with significant challenges noted in English and Science. Teachers' performance was influenced by gender, civil status, and training participation, while pupils' performance showed no direct correlation with teacher performance. Factors such as curriculum, supervision, and classroom management significantly affected teaching outcomes. Recommendations emphasize targeted instructional improvements and enhanced professional development for multigrade teachers.

Keywords: *Multigrade classes, Teacher performance, Pupil performance, Educational factors, Professional development*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching and learning are intricate processes that serve as the foundation of education. Teaching involves the systematic practice of behaviors by educators aimed at

fostering learning and development while learning signifies a relatively permanent behavior change driven by motivation and experience (Çakmak, 2016; Faizah, 2020; Alwis, et al, 2024)). Both are deeply intertwined psychological processes, central to a teacher's responsibilities, as learning is the ultimate objective of teaching. Teachers equipped with an understanding of developmental theories can create well-structured learning experiences that cater to individual learners' needs (Oja,1990; Roundtree, 2021).

The educative process revolves around three core components: the learner, who is the focal point of education; the teacher, who designs and delivers guided learning opportunities; and the learning environment, which encompasses the methods and resources used to achieve educational goals (Mugambi, et al, 2015)). Effective teaching requires teachers to possess content knowledge and the skills to manage diverse classroom dynamics and foster meaningful learning experiences (Gage & Macsuga-Gage, 2017)).

In the context of multigrade teaching, these challenges are magnified. Multigrade classes, where one teacher instructs multiple grade levels simultaneously, are often established in remote areas with low enrollment numbers and limited resources (Medequillo & Gallardo, 2024; Naparan, & Castañeda, 2021; Little, 2008). Despite its necessity, multigrade teaching demands advanced pedagogical skills, patience, and resourcefulness from teachers to address the diverse developmental needs of their students (Medequillo & Gallardo, 2024).

The Philippine Constitution, particularly Article XIV of the 1987 Constitution, underscores the critical role of education in shaping future generations, highlighting the importance of instilling patriotism, critical thinking, and vocational efficiency (Romero, 2008). Multigrade instruction aligns with these educational goals by ensuring that even learners in underserved areas receive quality education. However, multigrade teachers often face significant challenges, including a lack of specialized training, insufficient instructional materials, and limited support from school administrators (Napan, & Castañeda, 2021; Ramathan, & Ngubane, 2013).

The researcher, being a multigrade teacher in the City of Ilagan, observed that teaching in such settings presents unique hurdles. Explaining concepts effectively without adequate instructional materials and facilities is a recurring issue. Additionally, maintaining classroom discipline can be difficult, as younger students may be distracted by lessons intended for older peers, and older students might dominate discussions (Ramathan, & Ngubane, 2013; Urma, & Callo, 2023). Moreover, pupils often exhibit poor study habits and rely heavily on teacher-driven efforts, leading to suboptimal academic outcomes.

These observations underscore the urgency of addressing the performance of both teachers and pupils in multigrade settings. The study aims to evaluate the academic performance of pupils and the professional effectiveness of teachers in multigrade classes in the City of Ilagan. Furthermore, it seeks to identify factors influencing teacher performance, such as classroom management, instructional resources, and professional competencies, to improve multigrade instruction and ensure quality education

Conceptual Framework

Multigrade teaching requires a nuanced understanding of pedagogy to address the diverse needs of learners in a single classroom. Effective multigrade teachers must apply varied strategies tailored to pupils' developmental levels, learning needs, and abilities. (Naparan & Alinsug, 2020). However, these efforts are often hindered by limited resources, insufficient training, and inadequate administrative support, which adversely impact both teaching quality and pupil outcomes (Medequillo & Gallardo, 2024).

As highlighted by previous studies, the success of multigrade instruction depends heavily on the teacher's ability to manage classrooms, implement differentiated instruction, and engage students effectively (Naparan & Alinsug, 2020). Addressing these challenges requires targeted interventions, including professional development programs, improved instructional materials, and enhanced classroom facilities.

This study adopts a holistic approach to examine the factors affecting the performance of multigrade teachers and their pupils. By analyzing teacher profiles, instructional strategies, and academic outcomes, the research aims to identify actionable recommendations for enhancing multigrade education in the City of Ilagan. The findings are expected to contribute to the broader discourse on multigrade teaching, offering insights for policymakers, educators, and stakeholders committed to advancing educational equity and quality.

Research Questions

This study sought to find out the performance of pupils and teachers in the Multigrade Classes in the City of Ilagan.

Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the Multigrade teachers in terms of:
 - a. gender
 - b. age
 - c. civil status
 - d. highest educational attainment
 - e. number of years in teaching Multigrade classes
 - f. in-service training and seminars in Multigrade teaching?
2. What is the performance level of Multigrade teachers of the City of Ilagan?
3. What is the academic performance of the Multigrade pupils in the City of Ilagan?
4. Is there a significant difference in the performance of Multigrade teachers when grouped according to their profile?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the performance of Multigrade teachers and the performance of their pupils?
6. How do the following factors affect the performance of Multigrade teachers:
 - a. instruction
 - b. supervisory assistance extended
 - c. assessment and evaluation of learning
 - d. classroom management
 - e. physical facilities

f. teachers' competence in handling Multigrade classes?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The descriptive method of research was employed in the study. According to Krishnarao, (1961), this method of research is a fact-finding study with adequate and accurate interpretation of findings. It describes with emphasis what actually exists. This method is appropriate for the study, particularly in determining the factors that affect the performance of multigrade teachers.

Research Locale and Respondents of the Study

The research was conducted on multigrade teachers and pupils of Grades V and VI in the City of Ilagan.

Table1. Breakdown of the Respondents

SCHOOL	Teacher-respondents	Student-respondents
East District	8	77
South District	14	261
West District	12	138
TOTAL	34	476

Research Tools and Instruments

The primary instruments utilized in the study were structured questionnaires and interviews. The questionnaire consisted of two parts. Part one sought the profile of the respondents namely, gender, age, civil status, etc. Part two sought the factors affecting the teaching and learning of multigrade teachers, multigrade curriculum and instruction, supervisory assistance extended, assessment and evaluation of learning, classroom management, physical facilities and teacher competence in handling multigrade classes.

The academic performance of the pupils was based on their final rating in the five major subjects of English, Filipino, Math, Health and Science, and *Makabayan* which were taken from the Report on Promotion (Form 18e). The performance level of the multigrade teacher was indicated by the result of their evaluation of the CBPAST for the current year.

To gather more information from the respondents and crosscheck the information reflected in the questionnaire, the researcher also interviewed with the respondents.

Data Gathering Procedure

A letter of request and permission was forwarded through the principal to the Division Superintendent of the City of Ilagan to allow the conduct of the study and gathering of data. As soon as the request was granted, the researcher made the necessary communication to the teachers to schedule the administration of the questionnaire. A request letter was also sent asking for a copy of the teacher-respondents' CBPAST results and the academic performance of the pupil-respondents based on Form 18e (Report on Promotion).

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data gathered from the respondents were analyzed using the following statistical tools:

1. Frequency and Percentage was used on the profile of the respondents, namely gender, civil status, highest educational attainment, number of years in teaching multigrade classes and in-service trainings and seminars in multigrade teaching; and, the academic performance of multigrade pupils.
2. Weighted Mean was used on factors affecting the teaching of multigrade teachers in curriculum and instruction, in supervisory assistance extended, assessment and evaluation learning, classroom management, physical facilities, and, teacher competence in handling multigrade.
3. A chi-square test was employed to determine the significant difference in the performance of multigrade teachers when grouped according to profile. Also, it was used to determine the significant relationship between the multigrade teachers' performance and the academic performance of their pupils.

Data Analysis Procedure

- A. The performance of the multigrade teachers based on their latest CBPAST was analyzed using the following categories:

Appraisal Rating		Overall Performance Rating	
Numerical Value	Description	Weighted Average	Description
4	Highly Proficient (HP)	3.51 - 4.00	Outstanding (O)
3	Proficient (P)	2.51 - 3.50	Very Satisfactory (VS)
2	Basic (B)	1.51 - 2.50	Satisfactory (S)
1	Below Basic (BB)	1.00-1.50	Below Basic (BB)

- B. The academic performance of the pupils was analyzed based on the categories given below:

Range	Qualitative Description
Above 86	High

81-86	Average
Below 81	Low

C. The factors affecting the performance of Multigrade teachers were determined and analyzed using the following category:

Scale	Mean Range	Qualitative Description
5	4.20-5.00	Very much
4	3.40-4.19	Much
3	2.60-3.39	Fair
2	1.80-2.59	Not much
1	1.00-1.79	Not at all

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents

A. Teacher-Respondents

Table 2. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Teacher-Respondents by Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
26	2	5.9
27	2	5.9
28	2	5.9
29	2	5.9
31	2	5.9
32	2	5.9
33	3	8.8
35	2	5.9
36	3	8.8
37	2	5.9
38	3	8.8
39	5	14.7
54	2	5.9
56	2	5.9
Total	34	100.0
Average Age = 36 Years Old (20 Respondents or 52.9 % are 36 years old and below)		

Table 2 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of teacher-respondents by age. As seen from the table, the youngest Multigrade teachers, two (2) or 5.9 percent were 26 years old and the oldest, two (2) or 5.9 percent were 56 years old. The average age of the respondents was 36 years old, of which 20 or 52.9 percent were aged 36 years

old and below. The majority of the Multigrade teachers were 36 years old and below and are still considered young professional teachers.

Table 3. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Teacher-Respondents by Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	3	8.8
Female	31	91.2
Total	34	100.0

Table 3 shows that 31 of the 34 teacher-respondents or 91.2 were female and three (3) or 8.8 percent were male. This indicates that most of the Multigrade teachers are female, which shows that Multigrade teaching is handled by female teachers.

Table 4. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Teacher-Respondents by Civil Status

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	6	17.6
Married	28	82.4
Total	34	100.0

Table 4 is all about the civil status of the respondents. Twenty-eight (28) of the teacher-respondents were married and only six (6) or 17.6 are single. From these data, it can be inferred that Multigrade classes are assigned to married teachers probably because they are more experienced in handling children in multigrade than teachers of single status given the fact that most married teachers have their children, and they know more about how to deal with young pupils.

Table 5. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Teacher-Respondents by Number of Years in Service

Years in Service	Frequency	Percentage
1	4	11.8
2	4	11.8
4	4	11.8
5	2	5.9
8	8	23.5
14	6	17.6
16	2	5.9
26	2	5.9
27	2	5.9
Total	34	100.0
Average Years in Service = 10 Years (22 or 64.8 percent are in the service for 10 years & Below)		

Table 5 presents the number of years that the Multigrade teacher-respondents are in the service. Four (4) of the 34 teacher-respondents or 11.8 percent were in the service for 1 year, and two (2) or 5.9 percent had the longest year in service, having been in the service for 27 years. The average year that the Multigrade teacher-respondents have been in the service is 10 years. Twenty-two (22) or 64.8 percent had been in the service for 10 years and below. The majority of the respondents have been in the service for 10 years and below, which indicates that the current Multigrade teacher-respondents are still young in the service.

It is observed that in the DepEd, new teachers are assigned to multigrade schools, hence they are still young in the service.

Table 6. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Teacher-Respondents by Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Baccalaureate Degree	3	8.8
Baccalaureate Degree with MA units	6	17.6
Masters of Arts in Education	18	52.9
Master of Arts with Doctoral Units	4	11.8
Doctoral Degree	3	8.8
Total	34	100.0

The highest educational attainments of the Multigrade teacher-respondents are revealed in Table 6. As shown in the table, three (3) or 8.8 percent were Baccalaureate Degree holders; six (6) or 17.6 percent were Baccalaureate Degree holders with MA units; 18 or 52.9 percent were Master of Arts in Education; four (4) or 11.8 percent were Master of Arts with Doctoral units, and; three (3) or 8.8 percent had a doctorate. The majority of the Multigrade teacher-respondents were Master of Arts in Education. This connotes that multigrade teachers aim for professional advancement.

Table 7. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Teacher-Respondents by Highest Level of Multigrade Trainings/Seminars Attended

Highest Level of Training/Seminars Attended	Frequency	Percentage
National	2	5.9
Regional	2	5.9
Division	16	47.0
District	14	41.2
School	0	0.0
Total	34	100.0

Table 7 is the presentation of frequency and percentage distribution of the Multigrade teacher-respondents by the highest level of Multigrade trainings/seminars attended. As appeared in the table, two (2) or 5.9 percent attended trainings/seminars in the national level, two (2) or 5.9 percent at the regional level, 16 or 47.1 percent at the division level, and 14 or 41.21 percent at the district level. Most of the Multigrade teacher-respondents, 30 or 88.2 percent, attended training /seminars at the division/district level. This is an indication that the Department of Education in the Division of Isabela provides trainings/seminars to their teacher constituents.

B. Pupil-Respondents

Table 8. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Pupil-Respondents by Age

Age	Frequency	Percent
Below 11	65	13.7
11	93	19.5
12	290	60.9
Above 12	28	5.9
Total	476	100.0
Average Age = 12 years old (448 or 94.0 % have Ages 12 & Below)		

Table 8 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the pupil-respondents by age. As shown in the table, the youngest Multigrade pupil-respondents, 65 or 17.7 percent were below 11 years old, and the oldest, 28 or 5.9 percent were above 12 years old. 93 or 19.5 percent were 11 years old and 290 or 60.9 percent were 12 years old. The average age of the pupil-respondents was 12 years old of which 448 or 94.0 % were 12 years old and below. This is an indication that the majority of Multigrade VI pupils were at the right age in their year level.

Table 9. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Pupil-Respondents by Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	192	40.3
Female	284	59.7
Total	476	100.0

As shown in Table 10, the majority, 284 or 59.7 percent of the pupil-respondents were female, and, 192 or 40.3 percent were male. The data run consistent with the researcher's observation that more female children than male attend basic education.

Table 10. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Pupil-Respondents by Occupation of the Parents

Occupation	Father		Mother	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Farmer	274	57.56	274	57.56
Housekeeper	2	0.42	151	31.72
Laborer/Construction worker	94	19.75		
Security Guard	4	0.84		
Computer Technician	2	0.42		
OFW			27	5.67
Soldier/Police	2	0.42		
Teacher	1	0.21	1	0.21
Tricycle Driver	36	7.56		
Businessman/woman	41	8.61	23	4.83
Wood Carver	18	3.78		
Seamen	2	0.42		
Total	476	100	476	100

The data above show the occupation of parents of the pupil-respondents. As presented, 274 or 57.56 percent of the parents (both mother and father) of the pupil-respondents were farmers. Ninety-four (94) or 19.75 percent of the fathers were laborers/construction workers while 151 or 31.72 percent of the mothers were a housekeeper. Forty-one (41) or 8.61 percent of the fathers were a businessman; and, 23 or 4.83 percent of the mothers were engaged in business. Thirty-six (36) or 7.56 percent of the fathers were tricycle drivers, and 27 or 5.67 percent of the mothers were OFWs.

Most of the fathers and mothers of the pupil-respondents were farmers, indicating that the only means of sending their children for basic education is by tilling the land which is either their land or others’.

Table 11. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Pupil-Respondents by Dialect Spoken

Dialect Spoken	Frequency	Percent
Ilocano	348	73.1
Tagalog	42	8.8
Ybanag	86	18.1
Total	476	100.0

Table 11 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the pupils by dialect spoken. Of the 476 pupil-respondents, 348 or 73.1 percent were Ilocano speaking; 42 or 8.8 percent were Tagalog speaking, and; 86 or 18.1 percent were Ybanag speaking.

The dialect of the majority of the pupil-respondents is Ilocano which indicates that Isabela is dominated by Ilocano-speaking people.

Table 12. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Pupil-Respondents by Ordinal Position

Ordinal Position	Frequency	Percent
First	183	38.4
Second	136	28.6
Third	95	20.0
Fourth	25	5.3
Fifth	11	2.3
Sixth	12	2.5
Seventh	8	1.7
Eight	4	.8
Ninth	2	.4
Total	476	100.0

Table 12 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the pupil-respondents by ordinal position. The majority of the student respondents, 183 or 38.4 percent were the *first* child in the family, 136 or 28.6 percent were *second*, and 95 or 20.0 percent were *third*. The rest of the respondents were *fourth* to *ninth* in the ordinal position. The table indicates that the majority of the pupil-respondents are in the first order of the family children.

Table 13. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Pupil-Respondents by Number of Siblings

No. of Siblings	Frequency	Percent
1	64	13.4
2	173	36.3
3	123	25.8
4	66	13.9
5	18	3.8
6	14	2.9
7	4	.8
8	8	1.7
9	6	1.3
Total	476	100.0

Table 13 reveals the frequency and percentage distribution of the pupil-respondents by the number of siblings. As seen in the table, 64, or 13.4 percent belonged to a family with 1 sibling; 173, or 36.3 percent belonged to a family with 2 siblings; 123, or 25.8 percent were in a family with 3 siblings, and; 66, or 13.9 percent were in the family

with 4 siblings. The rest of the pupil-respondents belonged to families with 5 – 9 siblings. The majority of the pupil-respondents belonged to families of two and three siblings.

This indicates that most of the families involved in the study preferred to have two or three children only.

Table 14. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Pupil-Respondents by Monthly Income of Parents

Monthly Income	Frequency	Percent
Below 5,000.00	53	11.13
5,001.00 - 9,000.00	217	45.59
9,001.00 - 14,000.00	159	33.40
14,001.00 - 19,000.00	31	6.51
Above 19,000.00	16	3.36
Total	476	100.0
Average Monthly Income = P10, 000.00		

Table 14 reveals the monthly income of the parents of the pupil-respondents. As shown in the table, of the 476 pupil-respondents, 53 or 11.13 percent had a monthly income of below 5,000.00; 217, or 45.59 percent had 5,001.00 – 9,000.00; 159, or 33.40 earned 9,001.00 – 14,000.00; 31 or 6.51 percent had an income of 14,001.00 – 19,000.00; and, 16 or 3.36 had an income above 19,000.00. The majority of the parent’s monthly income ranged from 5,001 to 9,000.00. However, the average monthly income of the respondents was 10,000.00. This indicates that most of the pupil-respondents were within the regional poverty line.

Performance Level of Multigrade Teachers of the City of Ilagan

A. Latest CBPAST

Table 15. Mean Distribution of the Summary Rating of Teacher-Respondents by their Latest CBPAST

	Summary Rating	Mean	Description
I	INSTRUCTIONAL COMPETENCE	3.22	Proficient (P)
II.	SCHOOL, HOME, COMMUNITY LINKAGES	3.15	Proficient (P)
III.	PERSONAL, SOCIAL GROWTH AND PROFESSIONAL CHARACTERISTICS	3.33	Proficient (P)
	Overall Performance Rating	3.23	Proficient (P) / Very Satisfactory (VS)

The table above reveals the mean distribution of the summary rating of teacher respondents on the three major components of their latest CBPAST. As shown in the

table, the teacher respondents were more proficient in their personal, social growth, and professional characteristics as revealed by its highest mean of 3.33 as compared to the other components of instructional competence; and, school, home, and community linkages as indicated by its corresponding mean of 3.22 and 3.15.

Generally, the overall performance rating of the teacher-respondents on the latest CBPAST was “Very Satisfactory” or “Proficient” as indicated by the corresponding overall mean of 3.23. (See Appendix on the latest CBPAST).

Table 16. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Teacher-Respondents by their Overall Rating of Latest CBPAST

Overall Rating	Description	Frequency	Percentage
4	Outstanding (O)	12	35.29
3	Very Satisfactory (VS)	22	64.71
2	Satisfactory (S)	0	0.00
1	Below Basic (BB)	0	0.00
Total		34	100.00
Overall Mean = 3.23 (Very Satisfactory)			

Table No. 16 exhibits the frequency and percentage distribution of teacher-respondents by their overall rating of the latest CBPAST. Twelve or 35.29 percent of the respondents had their latest CBPAST of “Outstanding”; and, 22, or 64.71 percent were “Very Satisfactory”. The overall rating of the teacher respondents was “very satisfactory” as indicated by its corresponding mean of 3.23.

The majority of the teacher-respondents were “very satisfactory” in their CBPAST.

Academic Performance of the Multigrade Pupils in the City of Ilagan

The succeeding tables present the frequency and percentage distribution of the academic performance of the multigrade pupils in the City of Ilagan by the five (5) major subjects, namely: Filipino, English, Mathematics, Health and Science, and *Makabayan*.

Table 17. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Academic Performance of Multigrade Pupil-Respondents in Filipino

Academic Performance	Frequency	Percent
High (Above 86)	121	25.4
Average (81 - 86)	206	43.3
Low (Below 81)	149	31.3
Total	476	100.0

Table 17 reveals that 121 or 25.4 percent of the multigrade pupils got a “high” (Above 86) academic performance in Filipino; 206 or 43.3 percent had “average” (81-86)

performance; and, 149, or 31.3 got “low” (Below 81) academic performance. The majority of the respondents had an “average” academic performance in Filipino subjects.

Table 18. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Academic Performance of Multigrade Pupil-Respondents in English

English	Frequency	Percent
High (Above 86)	95	20.0
Average (81 - 86)	174	36.6
Low (Below 81)	207	43.5
Total	476	100.0

Table 18 exhibits that of the 476 multigrade pupils, 95, or 20.0 percent obtained “high” academic performance; 174, or 36.6 had an “average” academic performance; and, 207, or 43.5 percent had “low”. The majority of the multigrade pupils had “low” academic performance in English.

According to the respondents, one reason why they were low is that English is the medium of instruction. This is true of the result in NAT where the pupils performed low in English.

Table 19. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Academic Performance of Multigrade Pupil-Respondents in Mathematics

Mathematics	Frequency	Percent
High (Above 86)	97	20.4
Average (81 - 86)	218	45.8
Low (Below 81)	161	33.8
Total	476	100.0

Shown in Table 19 is the academic performance of the pupils in Mathematics. 97 out of 476 showed “high” academic performance in Math; 218 or 45.8 percent had “average” academic performance; and, 161, or 33.8 percent had “low” performance. Most of the pupils have an “average” academic performance in Mathematics.

Table 20. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Academic Performance of Multigrade Pupil-Respondents in Science & Health

Science & Health	Frequency	Percent
High (Above 86)	95	20.0
Average (81 - 86)	175	36.8
Low (Below 81)	206	43.3
Total	476	100.0

Table 20 shows the academic performance of pupils in Science & Health. Of the 476 pupils, 95, or 20.0 percent obtained “high” academic performance; 175, or 36.8 percent had an “average” academic performance; and, 206, or 43.3 percent got “low” academic performance. The majority of the pupils had a “low” academic performance in Science & Health.

This finding runs parallel in English. The teacher-respondents told the researcher that the medium of instruction is English which could be the reason for their low performance in said subject.

Table 21. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Academic Performance of Multigrade Pupil-Respondents in *Makabayan*

Makabayan	Frequency	Percent
High (Above 86)	158	33.2
Average (81 - 86)	267	56.1
Low (Below 81)	51	10.7
Total	476	100.0

Table 21 exhibits the academic performance of the pupils in the *Makabayan* subject. Out of 476, 158, or 33.2 percent performed academically “high”; 267, or 56.1 percent obtained “average” academic performance; and, 51, or 10.7 percent had “low” academic performance. The majority of the pupils got an average rating in their academic performance in *Makabayan*.

Table 22. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Multigrade Pupil- Respondents according to Overall Academic Performance

Overall Performance	Frequency	Percent
High (Above 86)	108	22.7
Average (81 - 86)	220	46.2
Low (Below 81)	148	31.1
Total	476	100.0

The table above reveals that of the 476 pupil-respondents, 108 or 22.7 obtained “high” academic performance, 220, or 46.2 percent had an “average” academic performance, and 148 or 31.1 percent had “low” academic performance. The majority of the pupils showed an overall academic performance of “average”.

Comparison in the Performance of Multigrade Teachers when Grouped according to their Profile

Table 23. Comparison in the CBPAST Performance of Multigrade Teachers Grouped According to Their Profile

Items	Significance Chi-square, C	Alpha A	Analyses	Decision	Significance
Gender	0.163	0.05	$C > A$	Ho is Accepted	Not Significant
Age	0.002	0.05	$C < A$	Ho is Rejected	Significant
Civil Status	0.680	0.05	$C > A$	Ho is Accepted	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	0.034	0.05	$C < A$	Ho is Rejected	Significant
Number of Years in Teaching Multigrade Classes	0.019	0.05	$C < A$	Ho is Rejected	Significant
In-service Trainings and Seminars Attended in Multigrade Teaching	0.072	0.05	$C > A$	Ho is Accepted	Not Significant

Table 23 shows the significant difference between the CBPAST Performance of Multigrade Teachers and their profile using the Chi-square test, at the level of significance Alpha A of 0.05.

The table reveals that the computed significance Chi-square C – values of 0.163, 0.680, and 0.072 are greater than the significance Alpha A of 0.05. The null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant difference between the CBPAST performances of the Multigrade teachers when grouped according to gender, civil status, and in-service trainings and seminars attended in Multigrade teaching.

However, for the profile age, highest educational attainment, and number of years in teaching Multigrade classes, the computed significance Chi-square values of 0.002, 0.034, and 0.019 are less than the given significance Alpha A of 0.05. The null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference between the CBPAST performance of Multigrade teachers when grouped according to their profile age, highest educational attainment, and number of years in teaching Multigrade classes.

The results indicate that the CBPAST performance of Multigrade teachers are not affected by their gender, civil status, and in-service trainings and seminars attended in Multigrade teaching, however, it is affected by profile age, highest educational attainment, and number of years in teaching Multigrade classes.

Relationship between the Performance of the Multigrade Teachers and the Performance of their Pupils

Table 24. Significant Relationship between the Performances of Multigrade Teachers and Multigrade Pupils

Items	Significance Pearson's χ^2 , C	Alpha A	Analysis	Decision	Significance
CBPAST of Teachers and Academic Performance of Multigrade Pupils	0.221	0.05	$C > A$	Ho is Accepted	Not Significant

Table 24 shows the significant relationship between the performance of Multigrade teachers and the performance of Multigrade pupils using the Chi-square test, at the level of significance Alpha A of 0.05.

The table reveals that the computed significance Pearson's Chi-square C – value of 0.221 between CBPAST of Teachers and Academic Performance of Multigrade Pupils rating are greater than the significance Alpha A of 0.05. There is no significant relationship between the CBPAST of Teachers and Academic Performance of Multigrade Pupils.

The result indicates that CBPAST of Teachers is independent of the academic performance of multigrade pupils. Thus, the academic performance of Multigrade pupils is not influenced by the performance of Multigrade teachers.

Factors Affecting the Performance of Multigrade Teachers

A. Curriculum Instruction

Table 25. Mean Distribution of the Effect of Factors on the Performance of Multigrade Teachers Along Curriculum Instruction

	Items	Mean	Description
1	Learning objectives and competencies are provided	4.00	Much
2	Time allotment for every subject is observed.	3.85	Much
3	Knowledge of the different learning areas is evident.	3.79	Much
4	Multigrade Handbook and Minimum Learning Competencies (MLC) copies are available.	2.82	Fair
5	Prototype Multigrade Lesson Plans are available.	2.88	Fair
6	Knowledge and skills in organizing the curriculum are developed	3.59	Much
7	There is ample time for preparing lessons.	3.00	Fair
8	Knowledge of the new approaches/ strategies in teaching multigrade is manifested.	3.79	Much
9	Values and Dep-Ed thrusts are integrated into teaching.	4.09	Much

10	Individualized instruction is conducted.	3.68	Much
	Mean	3.55	Much

Table 25 shows the mean distribution of the effect of the factors on the performance of the Multigrade Teachers along curriculum instruction. As shown above, the five top items “much” affecting the performance of Multigrade teachers along curriculum instruction were “values and DepEd thrusts are integrated into teaching”, “learning objectives and competencies are provided”, “time allotment for every subject is observed.”, “knowledge of the different learning areas is evident”, and “knowledge of the new approaches/ strategies in teaching Multigrade is manifested” as indicated by their respective means of 4.09, 4.00, 3.85, 3.79, and 3.79.

Generally, the performance of Multigrade teachers was “much” affected by the factors along curriculum instruction as indicated by the overall mean of 3.55. This can be attributed to the fact that the Multigrade teachers often integrate into their teaching the values and thrust of the DepEd, provide learning objectives and competencies, observe time allotment for every subject, and have knowledge of the different learning areas as manifested by their knowledge of the new approaches/strategies in teaching Multigrade classes.

B. Supervisory Assistance Extended

Table 26. Mean Distribution of the Effect of Factors on the Performance of Multigrade Teachers along Supervisory Assistance Extended

	Items	Mean	Description
1	Observance of the teacher at work is made.	3.76	Much
2	Guided and intensive supervision are made.	3.65	Much
3	Issuing classroom bulletin is done.	3.94	Much
4	Classroom visitation is made.	3.79	Much
5	Checking of lesson plans is conducted.	4.24	Very Much
	Mean	3.88	Much

Table 26 presents the mean distribution of the effect of the factors on the performance of the Multigrade Teachers along with the supervisory assistance extended. As shown in the table, the item that “*very much*” affected the performance of Multigrade teachers along with supervisory assistance extended was “checking of lesson plans is conducted” with a mean of 4.24. The items that affected “*much*” the performance of Multigrade teachers along with supervisory assistance extended were “issuing classroom bulletin is done”, “classroom visitation is made”, “observance of the teacher at work is made”, and “guided and intensive supervision are made.”, as indicated by their corresponding mean of 3.94, 3.79, 3.76, and 3.65.

Generally, the performance of Multigrade teachers was “*much*” affected by the factors along with supervisory assistance extended as indicated by the overall mean of

3.88. This can be qualified by the supervisor’s very frequent conduct of checking lesson plans of the teachers, and, the often issuance of classroom bulletins, classroom visitation, observation of teachers at work; and, guidance and intensive supervision to their Multigrade teachers.

C. Assessment and Evaluation of Learning

Table 27. Mean Distribution of the Effect of Factors on the Performance of Multigrade Teachers along Assessment and Evaluation of Learning

	Items	Mean	Description
1	Paper and pencil evaluation is conducted.	4.09	Much
2	There is a performance evaluation.	4.09	Much
3	Observation teaching is done.	3.76	Much
4	The interview is conducted.	3.50	Much
5	Opinionaire is written and submitted by the teacher.	3.44	Much
6	The questionnaire is completed by the teacher.	3.91	Much
7	A rating scale is conducted.	3.71	Much
	Mean	3.79	Much

Table 27 shows the mean distribution of the effect of the factors on the performance of the Multigrade teachers along assessment and evaluation of learning. As shown above, the items that “*much*” affected the performance of Multigrade teachers along with assessment and evaluation of learning were “paper and pencil evaluation is conducted”, “there is performance evaluation”, “questionnaire is accomplished by the teacher”, “observation teaching is done”, “rating scale is conducted”, “interview is conducted”, and “opinionaire is written and submitted by the teacher” with the mean 4.09, 4.09, 3.91, 3.76, 3.71, 3.50, and 3.44 respectively.

Generally, the performance of Multigrade teachers was “*much*” affected by the factors along with assessment and evaluation of learning as indicated by the overall mean of 3.79. This is due to the assessment of the supervisor of the Multigrade teachers in the conduct of paper and pencil evaluation, performance evaluation, teaching observation, interviews, and requiring teachers to submit their written opinion on matters requested of them.

D. Classroom Management

Table 28. Mean Distribution of the Effect of Factors on the Performance of Multigrade Teachers along Classroom Management

	Items	Mean	Description
1	Classroom instruction is well managed.	4.09	Much
2	The pupil’s instruction is managed.	4.03	Much
3	Good routine discipline is established.	3.97	Much

4	Classroom discipline is maintained.	3.97	Much
5	Any kind of misbehavior/ discontentment is directed.	3.91	Much
6	Individual needs are identified.	3.91	Much
7	Absenteeism among pupils is checked and monitored.	4.21	Very Much
8	Multi-personalities among students are carefully handled.	3.82	Much
9	A high incidence of dropout is reported.	3.71	Much
10	A reward system to deserving pupils is present.	4.29	Very Much
	Mean	3.99	Much

Table 28 shows the mean distribution of the effect of the factors on the performance of the Multigrade Teachers along classroom management. As shown in the table, the items that affected “*very much*” the performance of Multigrade teachers along classroom management were “reward system to deserving pupils is present” and “absenteeism among pupils is checked and monitored” as indicated by its mean of 4.29 and 4.21. “*Much*” affecting the performance of Multigrade teachers along classroom management was “classroom instruction is well managed.”, “pupil’s instruction is managed”, and “good routine discipline is established” as evinced by their corresponding means of 4.09, 4.03, and 3.97.

Generally, the performance of Multigrade teachers was “*much*” affected by the factors along classroom management as indicated by the overall mean of 3.99. This results from the Multigrade teachers giving rewards to deserving pupils and checking and monitoring always of the pupils’ absenteeism.

E. Physical Facilities

Table 29. Mean Distribution of the Effect of Factors on the Performance of Multigrade Teachers along Physical Facilities

	Items	Mean	Description
1	Textbooks and materials are adequately provided.	3.47	Much
2	Instructional materials are available.	3.76	Much
3	Classroom size for multi-ability pupils is determined.	3.71	Much
4	Physical facilities are available.	3.53	Much
5	Facilities for ancillary services are available.	3.35	Fair
6	Water facilities are present and well- maintained.	3.56	Much
7	Classroom ventilation and lighting are well-maintained.	3.76	Much
8	Playground facilities are available.	3.24	Fair
9	Comfort rooms are maintained.	3.91	Much
10	Guidance and medical services are present and availed of by the students.	3.62	Much
	MEAN	3.59	Much

Table 29 shows the mean distribution of the effect of the factors on the performance of the Multigrade Teachers along physical facilities. As shown above, the items that affected “*much*” the performance of Multigrade teachers along physical facilities were “comfort rooms are maintained”, “instructional materials are available”, “classroom ventilation and lighting are well-maintained”, “classroom size for multi-ability pupils is determined”, and, “guidance and medical services are present and availed of by the students.” as indicated by the means 3.91, 3.76, 3.76, 3.71, and 3.62 respectively.

Generally, the performance of Multigrade teachers was “*much*” affected by the factors along physical facilities as indicated by the overall mean of 3.59. This can be attributed to the maintenance of comfort rooms, availability of instructional materials, maintenance of classroom ventilation and lighting, determination of classroom size for multi-ability pupils, and the presence of guidance and medical services.

F. Teacher’s Competence in Handling Multigrade Classes

Table 30. Mean Distribution of the Effect of Factors on the Performance of Multigrade Teachers along Teachers’ Competence in Handling Multigrade Classes

	Items	Mean	Description
1	The teachers are proficient in the medium of instruction they use.	4.21	Very Much
2	Teachers are competent in teaching different subjects.	4.06	Much
3	They are creative in the use of appropriate instructional materials.	4.12	Much
4	They are proficient in the art of questioning.	4.21	Very Much
5	They give tests and assignments.	4.41	Very Much
6	They attend in-service training relative to multigrade teaching.	3.97	Much
7	They are able to use different teaching methods, strategies and techniques to meet individual needs and interests of pupils.	4.21	Very Much
8	They are knowledgeable of the new trends and methods of teaching Multigrade classes.	4.03	Much
	MEAN	4.15	Much

Table 29 displays the mean distribution of the effect of the factors on the performance of the Multigrade Teachers along with the teacher’s competence in handling Multigrade classes. As shown in the table, the items that affected “*very much*” the performance of Multigrade teachers along with Multigrade teacher’s competence in handling Multigrade classes were “they give tests and assignments”, “the teachers are proficient in the medium of instruction they use”, “ they are proficient in the art of questioning”, and “they can use different teaching methods, strategies, and techniques to meet individual needs and interests of pupils” as indicated by their corresponding means of 4.41, 4.21, 4.21, and 4.21.

Generally, the performance of Multigrade teachers was “*much*” affected by the factors along Multigrade teacher’s competence in handling Multigrade classes as indicated by the overall mean of 4.15. It can be noted that the performance of the Multigrade Teachers along teacher’s competence in handling Multigrade classes is affected when giving tests and assignments, using a proficient medium of instruction; being proficient in the art of questioning; and, using different teaching methods, strategies and techniques to meet individual needs and interest of pupils.

Conclusions

The study concludes that Multigrade teachers are predominantly young professionals, mostly female, who have pursued professional growth through master’s degrees and attendance at trainings and seminars. The pupil-respondents, primarily female Ilocano speakers, are of appropriate age for their grade level and come from low-income families with an average of three children. Multigrade teachers are proficient and perform their duties very satisfactorily, while pupils exhibit average performance across subjects such as English, Filipino, Science and Health, Math, and Makabayan. Teachers’ performance differences are influenced by gender, civil status, and participation in in-service trainings and seminars, but not by age, highest educational attainment, or years of experience in Multigrade teaching. Furthermore, the academic performance of Multigrade pupils is unaffected by their teachers’ performance. However, factors such as curriculum instruction, supervisory assistance, assessment and evaluation, classroom management, and physical facilities significantly impact the performance of Multigrade teachers.

Recommendations

Based on the above conclusions, the following are hereby recommended:

1. Since the multigrade pupils were found to have poorly performed in the subjects of English and Science, the Multigrade teachers are encouraged to focus more on these areas, giving more drills and exercises to enhance learning on the part of the Multigrade pupils.
2. Having shown an average academic performance in subjects Filipino, Math and *Makabayan*, the Multigrade pupils are also to be attended to by their teachers in these areas, giving the pupils more time to absorb concepts and put them into application.
3. As the overall academic performance of Multigrade pupils was found to be “average”, the Multigrade teachers are encouraged to attend more trainings and seminars relative to teaching in order to enhance their instructional competence thereby resulting in a higher academic performance of the pupils.
4. School administrators are likewise encouraged to extend full support in the training and professional development of multigrade teachers.
5. Since handling multigrade classes means dealing with different learners, the use of various techniques and strategies by multigrade teachers to suit the learners’ level and interest is very appropriate.

6. Given the complexity of multigrade instruction, a deeper study or investigation of it in a wider perspective and application is encouraged among teachers and school administrators.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher is committed to upholding the highest ethical standards throughout this study. Informed consent was carefully obtained from all participants, ensuring transparency and respecting their autonomy. Participants were assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any time, with strict measures in place to protect their anonymity and maintain confidentiality. The research process prioritized the well-being of participants, ensuring their safety and comfort at all stages. The researcher remained steadfast in maintaining integrity, avoiding plagiarism, and presenting findings impartially to minimize bias. The results of this study are intended solely to advance knowledge and are conducted in full compliance with ethical principles for the benefit of research and society.

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